

Religious Practices of the Valdivians during Ecuador's Early Formative Period

also known as "User The Valdivia religión during early formative of coastal ecuador"

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Entry tags: Andes, Religious Group, SUDamerican Tropics, Language, Unknown

Valdivia (circa 3500- 1300 B.C), is one of the earliest New World societies to transition from a hunter-gatherer economy to a fully agricultural one. They were sedentary and began the use of pottery technology. Over 2000 years span, the Valdivians inhabited and expanded from the Santa Elena Peninsula to the entire Pacific coast of Ecuador and into the low foothills of the western Andes. Archaeologists have divided the Valdivian era into 8 phases, with early periods (I-II) showing initial signs of shamanic or religious practices. This became more pronounced and sophisticated during the middle phases (III-VI). From this time onward, there is evidence of mound construction and the creation of ceremonial spaces around sunken plazas. Concurrently, in regions like the alluvial valleys of Julcuy, and la Emerenciana, civic-ceremonial mounds and platforms were erected. The tradition of mound-building persisted into the later periods, notably in the northern Manabí province at the site San Isidro. For the late Valdivia period, pottery bottles and other ceramic serving vessels appeared. In northern Manabí, this period coincides with the production of stone figurines of owls, often found alongside stone tablets depicting various patterns combining dots and lines.

Date Range: 3500 BCE - 1300 BCE

Region: Coastal Ecuador

Region tags: Andes

Expanded area of Valdivia along the Pacific Coast of Ecuador

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Stothert, K. E. (2003). Expression of Ideology in the Formative Period of Ecuador (J. Scott Raymond & Burger Richard, Eds.). *Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection*.
- Source 2: Zeidler, J. (2000). Gender, Status, and Community in Early Formative Valdivia Society. In and J. Y. Marcelo Canuto (Ed.), *The Archaeology of Communities* (pp. 161-181). Routledge.
- Source 3: Zeidler, J., Stahl, P., & Sutlif, M. J. (n.d.). Shamanistic Elements in a Terminal Valdivia Burial, Northern Manabí, Ecuador. Retrieved July 20, 2019, from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/301291029>

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Native-American-religion/South-America>

– Source 1 Description: About religious beliefs of Native South American Indians

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Native-American-religion/South-America>

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– No

Notes: This is an ancient society, already extinct

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Central plazas, ceremonial mounds

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– I don't know

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: mounds

Is iconography present:

– I don't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– I don't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– I don't know

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: Different types of tombs and body treatment

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:
– Yes

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:
– Yes

↳ Valuable items:
– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):
– Yes
Notes: Spondylus shell masks, and ornaments

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):
– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:
– Yes [specify]: Shell ornaments, obsidian, etc

↳ Other grave goods:
– Yes

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:
– Field doesn't know

- ↳ In cemetery:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Family tomb-crypt:
 - No
- ↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):
 - Yes
- ↳ Other formal burial type:
 - Yes [specify]: In some places, to capture water, associated to spondylus and strombus shells

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

- ↳ A supreme high god is present:
 - No
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– I don't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– I don't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Notes: It might be

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Circumcision:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Food taboos:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Hair:
– Yes
Notes: Female hairdoo

↳ Dress:
– Yes

↳ Ornaments:
– Yes
Notes: female figurines, animals and birds depicted in stone tablets

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

Other:

– Yes [specify]: Ritual paraphernalia, including snuff ornaments, spondylus.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: Valdivia started as a tribe, but within the sequence changed into a chiefdom organization

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than

the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Field doesn't know

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Religious Practices of the Valdivians during Ecuador's Early Formative Period, Meggers, Betty J., Clifford Evans, and Emilio Estrada. "Early Formative Period of Coastal Ecuador: The Valdivia and Machalilla Phases", no. 1 (1965). <https://doi.org/10.5479/si.00810223.1.1>.

Reference: Religious Practices of the Valdivians during Ecuador's Early Formative Period, "Producción Y Uso De La Cerámica Valdivia Fase VIII (complejo Piquigua), Del Sitio San Isidro Norte De Manabí, Ecuador", no. 2 (June 1, 2017). <https://doi.org/10.37135/chk.002.02.06>.

Reference: Religious Practices of the Valdivians during Ecuador's Early Formative Period, Stahl, Peter W.. "The Hallucinogenic Basis of Early Valdivia Phase Ceramic Bowl Iconography" 17, no. 2 (April 1985). <https://doi.org/10.1080/02791072.1985.10472329>.